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Nephropathic cystinosis in Iraqi children

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Abstract

Background: Nephropathy cystinosis is a rare, autosomal recessive lysosomal storage disorder caused by mutations in the CTNS gene that codes for a cystine transporter in the lysosomal membrane. Affected patients store 50-100 times the normal amounts of cystine in their cells, and suffer renal tubular and glomerular disease, growth retardation, photophobia, and other systemic complications, including a myopathy and swallowing dysfunction. The aim of this study is to describe the pattern of cystinosis in Iraqi children.

Patients and Methods: From 1999 to 2005 eight patients with Cystinosis were observed at the university hospital in Al Kadhimiyia. Their age ranged from 10 months to 14 years at the time of first referral. (Mean 5 years). The diagnosis of Cystinosis was confirmed by finding the pathognomic corneal cystine crystals on slit lamp examination.

Results: Three patients have evidence of Fanconi syndrome and one patient has evidence of RTA on referral. The remaining 4 patients had chronic renal failure on referral with 2 of them have reached end-

stage renal failure and have undergone dialysis. Four of the patients with Cystinosis have at least one sibling died from the same

illness. The remaining three patients had no family history of similar illness. All the patients have significant growth retardation with all of their growth parameters below the third centile. Among the patients with Cystinosis only one patient was receiving cysteamine sent to him from a relative living in UK. During the follow-up period, two of the patients with Cystinosis died from uremia. Only two of the 7 observed patients had the correct diagnosis of Cystinosis before referral. The remaining 5 patients were diagnosed as having RTA before referral indicating delay in referring the patients to the appropriate consultant.

Conclusion: The outcome of nephropathic cystinosis in Iraqi children is poor as most of them progressed to CRF because of the non-availability of cysteamine

Keywords: Fanconi syndrome--
Nephropathic -Cystinosis

Introduction

Cystinosis, clinically recognized since 1903, is a rare autosomal recessive lysosomal storage disease caused by mutations in CTNS. This gene codes for a lysosomal cystine transporter, whose absence leads to intracellular cystine crystals, widespread cellular destruction, renal Fanconi syndrome in infancy, renal glomerular failure in later childhood and

other systemic complications. Before the availability of kidney transplantation, patients affected with cystinosis uniformly died during childhood. After solid organ transplantations became successful in the 1960s, cystinosis patients survived, but eventually developed life-threatening consequences of the disease (e.g., swallowing disorders). **Since the introduction of cysteamine into the pharmacological management of cystinosis, well-treated adolescent and young adult patients have experienced normal growth and maintenance of renal glomerular function.** Cysteamine (and kidney transplantation) have commuted the death sentence of cystinosis into a nearly normal life with a chronic disease. Because treatment with oral cysteamine can prevent, or significantly delay, the complications of cystinosis, early and accurate diagnosis, as well as proper treatment, is critical [1, 2, 3, 4]. The aim of this study is to describe the pattern of cystinosis in Iraqi children.

Patients and Methods

From 1999 to 2005 eight patients with Cystinosis were observed at the university hospital in Al Kadhimiya. Their age ranged from 10 months to 14 years at the time of first referral. (Mean 5 years). The diagnosis of Cystinosis was confirmed by finding the pathognomic corneal cystine crystals on slit lamp examination.

Results

Three patients have evidence of Fanconi syndrome and one has evidence of proximal RTA on referral. The remaining 4 patients had chronic renal failure on referral with 2 of them have reached end-stage renal failure and underwent dialysis. Four of the patients with Cystinosis have at least one sibling died from the same illness. The remaining 4

patients had no family history of similar illness. All the patients have significant growth retardation with all of their growth parameters below the third centile. One patient developed severe bowing deformities interfered with mobilization. Table (1) shows the characteristics of the 8 patients with cystinosis.

Among 13 the patients with Cystinosis (8 referred to us and 5 of their siblings) only one patient was receiving cysteamine sent to him from a relative living in UK. During the follow-up period, two of the patients with Cystinosis died from uremia. Only 3 of the 8 observed patients had the correct diagnosis of Cystinosis before referral and the diagnosis in these 3 patients was suggested by the ophthalmologist after the development of photophobia rather by the treating physician. The remaining 5 patients were diagnosed as having RTA before referral indicating delay in referring the patients to the appropriate consultant.

A girl with Nephropathic cystinosis and chronic renal insufficiency.

Table (1) shows the characteristics of the 8 patients with cystinosis.

	Gender	Age at referral	Diagnosis before referral	Presentation on referral	Family history	Mortality
1	female	4 years	RTA	Proximal RTA	Negative	A live –ESRF
2	male	10 months	RTA	Fanconi syndrome	Negative	A live
3	female	2 year	RTA	Renal insufficiency	Negative	-----
4	male	1 year	Cystinosis	Fanconi syndrome	Brother died 1 week before referral at the age of 1 year	-----
5	male	11 years	cystinosos	ESRF	Brother died before the age of 10	Died from uremia
6	female	2 years	cystinosos	Fanconi syndrome	Negative	-----
7	female	14 years	RTA	CRF and skeletal deformities	2 sisters died before 7 years	Died from uremia
8	male	4	RTA	CRF	Bother died	-----

A boy with cystinosis and Fanconi syndrome

Discussion

Before the availability of kidney transplantation, patients affected with cystinosis uniformly died during childhood. After solid organ transplantations became successful in the 1960s, cystinosis patients survived, but eventually developed life-threatening consequences of the disease (e.g., swallowing disorders). Since the introduction of cysteamine into the pharmacological management of cystinosis, well-treated adolescent and young adult patients have experienced normal growth and maintenance of renal glomerular function. **Oral cysteamine therapy is given at doses of 60 - 90 mg/kg/day q.i.d. every 6 h, and generally achieves approximately 90% depletion of cellular cystine, as**

measured in circulating leucocytes. Cysteamine (and kidney transplantation) have commuted the death sentence of cystinosis into a nearly normal life with a chronic disease. Because treatment with oral cysteamine can prevent, or significantly delay, the complications of cystinosis, early and accurate diagnosis, as well as proper treatment, is critical.

In this study most patients were not diagnosed before referral and was referred relatively late. Cysteamine is generally not available in Iraq. Renal replacement therapy is also not available for children with cystinosis when they eventually reach end-stage renal failure. Among 13 the patients with Cystinosis (8 referred to us and 5 of their siblings) only one patient was receiving cysteamine

Conclusion: The outcome of Nephropathic cystinosis in Iraqi children is poor as most of them progressed to CRF because of the non-availability of cysteamine.

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